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**ASSESSMENT OF ONLINE TEACHING READINESS OF BUSINESS EDUCATION LECTURERS IN
MODIBBO ADAMA UNIVERSITY – YOLA ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study examined the perceived readiness of business education lecturers to effectively teach using the online medium. The study takes the qualitative approach and employed the case study design where 26 lecturers of business education programme in Modibbo Adama University Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria formed the population of the study. Purposive approached for data collection was employed and the instrument used for the data collection was a structured interview. Two objectives and two research questions guided the study. The researchers collected information through direct contact with the respondents, Content analysis and descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data, and results suggested that lecturers of business education programme in the institution under study are generally well disposed towards teaching using online medium and that majority of the lecturers have competency to teach using online platforms. The study recommended that university lecturers should strive more in personal drive to improve their competencies to teach online by engaging in self-skills enrichment effort and collaborative work with colleagues considered competent in doing so. The study also recommended that the management of universities should improve further on the needed infrastructure that will make teaching and learning online easier and less expensive for lecturers to shoulder.

Keywords: Lecturers, Competency, Attitude, Online, Perception

Introduction

The process of facilitating learning process at the university level rest largely on the shoulders of university lecturers, who are expected to be self-conscious in aligning their operational competences with the dynamic nature of the educational system. It is therefore essential for Lecturers to up their ability in adapting to new approaches in developing, organizing, delivering, and evaluating courses and learning materials in their field of expertise. The ever-increasing demand for educational opportunities points to the fact that the four walls of the lecture-room will no longer be sufficient for access, quality and efficiency in educational service provision, hence the need to leveraging on technological intermediaries in the teaching process. The advent online platforms for teaching purposes have demystify instructional time and space with the capacity to engage students through virtual interface set the stage for paradigm shift (Easton, 2013). As such a typical Nigerian university lecturer has to evaluate himself and reenact himself in order to match his competencies with the most recent medium of lesson delivery to remain confidently competent.

Competency is a knowledge, skill or ability that enables one to effectively perform the activities of a given occupation or function to the standards expected in employment (Richey, Fields, & Foxon, 2016). A number of researchers

have established areas of competencies for proficiency in online technologies for instruction purposes (Guasch, Alvarez, & Espasa, 2010), for one to venture effectively in that regard, the need for skills in pedagogical domain, communication and interaction ability, designing/planning function of leaning process, social function, instructive function, technological capability, and management domain are basic. The four core areas of competences that determines the preparedness of a lecturer to master the online teaching platform that are of interest to this researcher as suggested by (Gomes 2015) are course design, course communication, time management, and technical know-how.

State of preparedness of university lecturers in this text can be seen as readiness to tech online as posited by (Martin, Budhrani, & Wang 2019). Lecturer's perceived preparedness and the complementary nature of the environment within which they operate coupled with experiences and attitude, derived through training and the deliberate attempt to foster learning and collaborative teaching are capable of ensuring a rich learning environment in a context that identifies individual characteristics and contextual considerations best for anchoring online instructional platforms. The perceived self-efficacy of lecturers will strengthen the lecturer's confidence to function well where the need arises and where the needed environment is provided.

Lecturer's attitude towards delivering lessons online in high institution may be subjected to multiple problems (Martin, Budhrani, & Wang 2019), this need for attitudinal conformity to online approach in teaching constitutes major changes in lecturer's important role that is evidently inevitable. Such eminent transformation process that requires innate willingness to adapt to change at any level, would be characterized by complicated organization of individuals, institutional, and cultural factors as observed by (Clay, 2012). To understand lecturer's' perceived readiness for online teaching in more detail, examining their relations to the factors listed above are critical. Moreover, these factors may not affect all lecturers in the same way. Lecturers in higher education are not a homogeneous, the different important relationships affecting one group may be completely different for another, given different backgrounds, experience with and exposure to technology and the uniqueness of each academic discipline. This is exactly why this study is focused on the business education lecturers in Modibbo Adama University Yola, for immediate comprehension of their situation at hand for reasonable impact.

Teaching a course online involves more than replicating classroom strategies in a different form. It requires a different approach that focuses less on the amount of time students spend together in a particular place, and more on facilitating a process and on activities designed for students working interactively while individual students' differences in terms of difficulty is monitored and cared for by the lecturers University of Toledo (2017). It is therefore, noteworthy to consider whether the lecturers are ready to assimilate the fast-growing technology for teaching. There are a wide range of computer software, educational applications, multi-media and hyper-media resources from the net and World Wide Web that can be utilized to maximize the teaching-learning experience. Have business education lecturers evolved and are capable to manage such techniques in teaching? What is their innate self-desire and self- assurance to anchor the teaching process on a virtual platform for a successful result?

Lecturers' preparedness as a state of their competency for online teaching within the context of this study, was focused on two aspects of preparedness; that is the lecturers' attitude on the significant place of online teaching and additionally the lecturers' perception of their ability to confidently teach online. Attitude refers to the viewpoint a person has about something and its personal relevance to them (Ally, 2014). Ability has reference to the capacity to successfully perform (Anderson, 2015). Since measuring faculty's direct ability may not be entirely possible, we focused on their

perception of their ability to teach online. Several researchers have attempted to examine the relationships between attitude, ability, and readiness (Bayram & Comek, 2012; Espasa, & Meneses, 2012). However, researchers have not yet fully examined the relationships between attitude, competency and online teaching readiness particularly as it relates to the vocational business education lecturers in this part of the world.

Statement of Problem

Attitudinal laxity pushes oneself to the limit in an effort to yield to a new way of delivering lessons is one difficulty that prevents lecturers from trying to teach online. Of course, (Ken, 2021) indicated that there are no concerns with young instructors' tech knowledge. However, it is one of the most difficult aspects of virtual teaching for teachers, especially those who are 45, 50, and 55 years old. Therefore, it is crucial to draw the conclusion that researchers like (Teo, 2012) were suggestive of the fact that some lecturers' preference for ICT-based teaching as a pedagogical framework is based on their perception of the utility and simplicity of technological tasks.

Lack of confidence, competence, and resource accessibility are the three main challenges identified by Bingimlas (2018) as reasons why virtual interfaces cannot be fully utilized. However, Gomes (2015) listed the main barriers that prevent teachers from fully utilizing online platforms for teaching, including a lack of pedagogical and didactic training in how to use information and communication technology in the classroom. When it comes to the quest for teacher training in vocational business education, these impediments may very well be the same tale for academics at Modibbo Adama University. As a result, purposeful effort is required to promote competences in technologically enhanced instructional practices and to ascertain how readily predisposed the lecturers at the centre of this study are, this study titled "Assessment of online teaching readiness of business education lecturers in Modibbo Adama university – Yola Adamawa State, Nigeria" becomes imperative.

Objectives of the Study

This study sought to assess the competences of business education lecturers to effectively teach using the online medium. Its specific objectives were:

1. To assess the attitudes of business education lecturers towards online teaching.
2. To examine the perceived competency of business education lecturers to teach online.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the attitudes of business education lecturers towards online teaching?
2. What is the perceived competency of business education lecturers to teach online?

Literature review

Literatures points out that teaching in the online environment requires different competencies than in the face-to-face environment, particularly in the areas of technology, convergence, and engagement (Ko & Rossen, 2017). Hung and Jeng (2013) studied the intention of educational technology doctoral students to participate in online teaching. Results showed that doctoral students were not deterred from teaching online simply because they did not have the skills, as they assumed that they would be able to learn how to teach online in training sessions before delivering an online course.

In a systematic review of related publications, Chugh (2010) developed a concept matrix for online teaching readiness: affective dispositions, pedagogical approaches, and organizational orientations. Affective concepts include behaviours such as risk taking, accepting change or dealing with stress. Sharing and conversing online with students are examples of pedagogical approaches. Organizational orientations pertain to structure or time management. In their review, the authors classified five areas of research found in the literature: online teaching evaluations; instructors' identity and beliefs; transition to online learning; effective online teaching; and competencies for online teaching.

Relative to the items postulated above are other factors that influence teachers' positive attitudes toward teaching online and as put by (Clay, 2019), are prior experience teaching online, availability of online courseware, improved training and facilities, feedback from students, and flexibility of time and teaching schedules. The study by Shea (2017) showed that the number of times faculty had taught online was an important consideration in how motivated they are. and with more experience in the online modality, self-confidence levels increase.

Since teaching in the online modality is different from teaching in the classroom, faculty competencies to teach online require faculty to adjust their attitudes towards technology and teaching. It is essential to examine faculty attitudes on the importance of the various competencies for online teaching. Students are likely to experience more positive learning outcomes when their faculty have positive attitudes towards online course delivery (Volery, 2015). Denis, Watland, Pirotte, & Verday (2014) reported that respondents rated competencies that promote student interaction and build student-instructor relationships as most important. In the study by Denis (2014), respondents rated pedagogical roles as most important. A study by Darabi (2016) showed that faculty place most importance on managerial aspects of teaching, such as keeping records and maintaining course accuracy; the top-five tasks their respondents rated as important included reviewing the course for accuracy, assessing learners' attainment of learning objectives, and maintaining expertise in their subject area.

Methodology

The study takes the qualitative approach. It employed the case study design where 26 lecturers of business education programme in Modibbo Adama University Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria formed the population of the study. Purposive sampling approach was used for data collection. Qualitative design was chosen in order to get information about the Lecturers' opinions, feelings and practical experiences on their online teaching readiness. Instrument used was structured interview method. The questions were divided into two sections in line with the two research questions. The researchers collected information through direct contact with the lecturers and through phone calls. The respondents' responses were written down and formed the data which were categorized accordingly. Content analysis and descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data. The content analysis method at the basic level helped in describing what was said by the participants without any inferred interpretations. Descriptive statistics were also used to answer the research questions.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1

What are the attitudes of business education lecturers towards using online teaching mediums?

Table 1: Lecturers attitude towards online teaching.

S/N	Items	No. of Yes	No. of No	Total
1	Are you a proponent of total shift from face-to-face teaching to Online classes?	14	12	26
2	Do you think teaching online is the future of teaching and Learning process?	19	7	26
3	Have you put in personal effort to know how to improve your ability to teach online?	23	3	26
4	Is it difficult for you to grasp the online learning mechanisms?	22	4	26
5	Do you find pleasure in shouldering cost associated with learning how to teach online?	11	15	26
6	Would you find it easy shouldering cost associated with teaching your students online?	10	16	26
	Total	99	57	156
	Percentage total	63%	37%	100%

Source: Researcher’s Survey (2023)

Opinions derived from the interview sessions that was summarized in table 1, suggests that lecturers largely have positive attitude towards online teaching with 63% of the respondents indicating a desirable attitude towards teaching online and only 37% indicated poor attitude towards teaching online particularly as regards items 5 and 6 relating to the pleasure of shouldering personally the cost of continues learning and anchoring the teaching process using online mediums.

Research Question 2

What is the perceived competency of business education lecturers to teach online?

Table 2: Lecturers perceive capability to teach using online platforms.

S/N	Items	No. of Yes	No. of No	Total
1	Do you have the ability to send announcements/email reminders to course participants?	23	3	26
2	Can you create and moderate discussion forums with students?	19	7	26
3	Do you have the ability to respond to student questions promptly (within 24 to 48 hours)?	18	8	26
4	Do you have the ability to develop an online course orientation?	15	11	26
5	Can you use any feature in learner management system in order to manage time (e.g., online grading, rubrics, Speed Grader, calendar)?	10	16	26
6	Do you possess the ability to use course roster in the learning management system to set up teams/groups?	11	15	26
7	Are u conversant with at least two online collaborative tools (e.g. Google classroom, teachable, skills share, edX, Moodle, Udemy)?	21	5	26
Total		117	65	182
Percentage total		64%	36 %	100%

Source: Researcher’s Survey (2023)

Opinions derived from the interview sessions that was summarized in Table 2 suggests that majority of the teachers (64.3% precisely) claim they were of the belief that they possess the competences to facilitate their classes online while 36% of respondents indicated they are not fully ready to facilitate lessons online particularly as it regards the use of features in learner management system and course roster also in learner management system.

Discussion of Findings

Results from table one indicates that lecturers of business education have relatively good attitude towards teaching their students online and their attitude is a prelude to an action based on strong intrinsic interest and this finding and opinion coincides with the stand expressed by Volery (2015), that students are likely to experience more positive learning outcomes when their tutors have positive attitudes towards online course delivery. Certainly, for teaching online to take its rightful place in Nigerian universities, particularly among business education lecturers, deliberate desire to foster the process most steam from the part of the lecturers before any complementary modalities can be of importance.

The findings in table 2 above indicates specifically that business education lecturers who partook in this study perceived themselves as being ready and capable with the competences to anchor the business education learning content on the online teaching platforms and that is very essential for the effective course delivery online. This finding may not be far from the findings and opinion of Denis, Watland, Pirotte, & Verday (2014) who reported in a study that respondents

rated competencies that promote student interaction and build student instructor relationships as most important. Darabi (2014), in a different study, recorded that respondents rated pedagogical roles as most important as the study showed that respondents placed importance on managerial aspects of teaching, such as keeping records and maintaining course accuracy; including reviewing the course for accuracy, assessing learners' attainment of learning objectives.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made by the researchers based on the findings of the study:

1. University lecturers should strive more in personal drive to improve their competencies to teach online by engaging in self-skills enrichment effort and collaborative work with colleagues considered competent in doing so.
2. The management of universities should improve further on the needed infrastructure that will make teaching and learning online easier and less expensive for lectures to shoulder.

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